

DIMETHYLAMINO- AND DIETHYLAMINOPHENYLIMINO-CAMPHORS. REAGENTS FOR MERCURY.

By MAHAN SINGH.

Ammonium nitrosophenylhydroxylamine (*Bull. soc. chim. Belg.*, 1930, 39, 170) forms an insoluble compound with mercury and has been used for its estimation. It gives a similar insoluble product with a number of other metals and therefore cannot be regarded as a specific reagent for mercury.

p-Dimethylaminobenzylidene rhodamine (*Monatsh.*, 1905, 26, 1203) is another reagent used for mercury, silver and copper (ous). Mercurous ions give in neutral or acid solution a brilliant purple colouration. Mercuric ions yield a reddish colour in neutral solution or in the presence of dilute nitric acid. This colour is discharged by hydrochloric acid.

Diphenylcarbazone (*Compt. rend.*, 1908, 146, 754) also has been used for the detection of mercury, but a number of metals interferes with the detection of small amounts of mercury.

Dimethylamino- and diethylaminophenyliminocamphors (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 219, 768) add to the list of the compounds used for the detection of mercury.

The alcoholic solution (1%) of the dimethyl compound gives a deep scarlet colour with a mercuric salt. The reagent does not give any indication with Pb, Cu, Ni, Co, Fe, Ca, Ba, Cd, Mn and Mg salts. Bismuth and silver salts give a faint pink colouration along with a small amount of a white precipitate.

The diethyl compound, however, gives a deep violet colouration with mercurous and mercuric salts. This colour vanishes when a stream of oxygen is passed into the solution and reappears on adding a small amount of the reagent.

Detection of Mercury by the Spot Reaction.—Filter paper strips are soaked in 0.5% solutions of these compounds and are dried in the atmosphere. A drop of the mercuric salt solution gave a rich pink coloured spot which vanished on exposure to the vapours of ammonia. The depth of the colour is proportional to the amount of mercury present. This reaction is sensitive to one part of HgCl_2 in 50,000 parts of water.

A drop of mercurous nitrate solution, however, gave a pink saw-like tinge round a white spot. On exposure to ammonia the spot changed to black. The sensitiveness of this reaction is of the same order.